

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF *VICHARCHIKA* WITH *VIRECHANA* ALONG WITH *SHAMANA AUSHADI* W.S.R. TO ATOPIC ECZEMA - A CASE STUDY

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Article Received on 02 May 2026,
Article Revised on 22 May 2026,
Article Published on 01 June 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20442372>

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How to cite this Article: *¹Aakriti Sharma, ²Binisha C., ³V. K. Kori. (2026). Ayurvedic management of *vicharchika* with *virechana* along with *shamana aushadi* w.s.r. To atopic eczema - a case study, World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(6), 544-556.

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ABSTRACT

Background - *Vicharchika* is a type of *Kshudra Kushtha* characterized with symptoms namely *Kandu*, *Srava*, *Pidika* and *Shyava Varna*. *Vicharchika* is often correlated to eczema based on the clinical presentations. Its prevalence in children varies from 0.7% to 26%, while in adult it may range from 1% to 3%. The clinical presentation of *Vicharchika* similar to Eczema in modern dermatology. Eczema (also called atopic dermatitis) is characterized by dry itchy skin with areas of poorly demarcated erythema and scale. Ayurveda offers treatment for the root of eczema by cleansing vitiated Dosha and balancing the Dosha and Dhatus. *Virechana* is mentioned as *Shodhana* management of *Kushtha Roga* and as *Pitta* is predominant in *Vicharchika*, *Virechana* serves great benefits. **Patient Information** – A 13-year-old female patient visited KB OPD of Kaumarbhritya

department with presenting complaints of dry lesions with itching all over body and Maculopapular lesion reddish colour in interphalangeal region for 6 months. Based on history and clinical findings, the case was diagnosed as *Vicharchika*. **Intervention** – The patient was managed with Ayurvedic treatment protocol, *Shodhana* with *Virechana* and *Shamana* therapy. **Results** – During treatment relief was seen after *Shodhana*. Symptoms were relieved by 80% after taking 30 days of *Shamana* medication. POEM and DLQI Score were reduced

significantly after treatment. **Conclusion** – In this patient, A protocol of *Shodhana* and *Shamana* shows significant relief in present patient of *Vicharchika*.

KEYWORDS: Eczema in children, *Kushtaroga*, *Vicharchika*, *Virechana*.

INTRODUCTION

Most of the skin diseases in Ayurveda have been compiled under *Kushtha Roga* or *Kshudra Roga*. *Vicharchika*, which can be correlated with Atopic eczema, is one among the types of *Kushtha Roga*. Atopic dermatitis, more commonly known as atopic eczema, is a chronic, relapsing inflammatory skin disorder characterized by dry skin, localized erythematous rash, and intense pruritus. As one of the most common skin disorders globally, atopic dermatitis poses a significant clinical and economic burden on affected patients. Atopic eczema or atopic Dermatitis, a common skin disease, affects about 15 to 30% children and adolescents worldwide. This disease often begins in infancy. The phase 3 International Study of Asthma and Allergy in Children (ISAAC) has reported 2.7% overall prevalence of current eczema among Indian children aged 6-7 years and 3.6% among Indian children aged 13 -14 years.^[1]

There is no single cause of atopic dermatitis. The aetiology is complex involving an interplay between genetics, impaired epidermal skin barrier, dysregulated immune system, and altered skin microbiome.^[2,3] In fact, Atopic Dermatitis is more recently regarded as a systemic disorder associated with increased risks of developing both allergic and nonallergic comorbidities.^[4] General measures for all patients include trigger avoidance, enhancing skin barrier function and skin hydration with moisturizers/emollients, education on proper medication use and adherence, and controlling pruritus and acute flares. The mainstay of treatment includes topical anti-inflammatories and topical corticosteroids.^[5]

Vicharchika is a skin ailment where *Pidika* (eruptions) over the skin appear with *Shyavta* (dark pigmentation), *Kandu* (itching) and with *Bahusrava* (profuse discharge) as per Acharya Charaka.^[6] As per Acharya Sushruta, it is a condition in which the skin has *Raji* (linear rough lesions) with *Atikandu* (intense itching), *Daha* (burning sensation) and *Atiruja* (pain).^[7] Acharya Vagbhata also mentioned similar symptoms.^[8] Acharya Bhela described *Vicharchika* as Reddish deep-rooted lesion i.e. *Mamserupachita* accompanied with oozing. The pathogenesis includes vitiation of *Tridosha*, predominantly *Kapha* as per Acharya Charaka and *Pitta* as per Acharya Sushruta, along with involvement of *Rakta*, *Mamsa*, and *Lasika*

Dhatu, leading to chronicity and recurrence. In *Kushtha* repeated *Shodhana* is indicated due to *Bahu Doshavastha* in order to eliminate the aggravated *Dosha*.^[9]

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The treatment protocol was formulated in accordance with Ayurveda with reference of classical Samhitas along with contemporary literature and relevant research articles for the effective management of case of *Vicharchika*.

Objective: Ayurvedic management of *Vicharchika* with *Virechana* along with *Shamana Aushadhi* w.s.r. to Atopic Eczema.

Patient information: An 13years old female patient came to Kaumarbhriya OPD No.15 presenting with complaints of dry and rough lesion all over body and reddish Maculo-papular lesion majorly present at Inter-phalangeal region associated with severe itching and burning presentation leading to watery discharge.

History of Present illness: The patient was apparently healthy one year ago, after which she developed dry and rough lesion all over body starting as reddish maculo-papular lesion over Inter-phalangeal region associated with itching and burning sensation leading to watery discharge. Patient consulted local physician and was treated with topical moisturising cream, oral medications and anti-histamine medicine, and got symptomatic relief. However, after discontinuing treatment, the symptoms relapsed. Then patient then comes to ITRA Hospital for Ayurvedic management.

History of past illness: No history on any other major illness like asthma, tuberculosis and any major systemic illness.

History of family illness: Younger sister also has similar complaints for past 4 months.

Personal History

- Bowel- Regular 1 time/day
- Urine- Normal 6-7 time/day
- Appetite- Good
- Sleep- Disturbed for some in night due to itching.

Diet History

Packet food-1pack/day; Maggie 1-2times/weeks; Sour fruits-everyday; Outside food- 1 time/week.

Examination**General Examination**

Build- Normal

Posture & Gait-Normal

P⁰T⁰C⁰C⁰L⁰E⁰

Vitals

Heart Rate – 76/min

Respiratory Rate – 24/min

BP – 120/70 mm of Hg

Temperature – 97.4oF

Anthropometry: Weight – 34.6 kg, Height – 159 cm, BMI – 13.68

Systemic examination: No any abnormality detected

Integumentary Examination

Type of lesion: Both primary lesions and secondary lesions were present

Distribution: Asymmetrical

Associations: Itching – Present (sever at night), pain – absent, discharge – watery burning – present

Morphology: Dry and rough lesions all over body with darkening of skin in patches and Maculo-papular lesion reddish in colour, irregular with indistinct margins, crusty layer over lesions in inter-phalangeal region.

Site of Lesion: All over body, Inter-phalangeal region.

Colour of lesion: Dark patches on dry and rough skin, reddish lesion in interphalangeal region.

Shape: oval to Irregular shape

Size: Vary in size (approximately 1cm to 3 cm in diameter)

Ashtavidha Pariksha

Nadi- Vata Pitta (pulse – 94 bpm)

Mala- 1 times/day

Mutra- 6-7 times/day

Jihva- *Alpa Saam* (coated)

Shabda- *Spashta*

Sparsha- *Anushna Sheeta*

Druk- *Prakrita*

Aakriti- *Madhyama*

Dashvidha Pariksha

Prakriti- *Vata Pitta*

Vikriti Dosh- *Tridosha*.

Dushya- *Rasa, Rakta*.

Sara- *Madhyama*

Samhanana- *Madhyama*

Pramana- *Prakrita*

Satwa- *Avara*

Satmya- *Madhyama*

Aahara Shakti: (*Abhyavaharana, Jarana Shakti*)- *Madhyama*

Vyayama Shakti- *Madhyama*

Vaya- *Bala*

Samprapti Ghatkas

Doshas - *Tridosha*

Dushya - *Twak, Rakta, Mansa, Lasika*

Srotas - *Rasa, Rakta, mansa & Udakavaha*

Agni - *Jatharagni & Dhatwagnimandya*

Srotodusti - *Sang & vimargagamana*

Sanchara - *Tiryaga sira*

Adhishtana - *Twaka*

Rogamarga - *Bahya*

Swabhava - *Chirkari*

Diagnostic Assessment

On local examination Dry and rough skin all over body and blackish Maculo-papular lesion over inter-phalangeal region which were irregular and with indistinct margins. The *Lakshana*

of *Vicharchika* like *Kandu* (itching), *Shyava Pidika* (dark lesion), *Srava* (discharge), *Rukshata* (dryness) were present. Based on clinical presentation, the case diagnosed as *Vicharchika Kushtha* (Atopic Eczema).

Assessment Criteria

Subjective criteria: Patient was observed for improvement in dry and scaly lesion along with improvement in associated complaints like itching and pain.

Objective criteria

1. POEM – Patient-Oriented Eczema Measure.^[10]
2. DLQI – Dermatology Life Quality Index

Therapeutic intervention

Table 1.0: Timeline of therapeutic intervention.

Sr. No.	Karma	Intervention	Medication/ procedure	Duration
1.	<i>Shodhana Karma</i>	<i>Deepana– Pachana</i>	<i>Chitrakadi Vati</i>	3 Days
		<i>Abhyantara Snehapana</i>	<i>Go Ghrita</i>	7 Days
		<i>Sarvanga Abhyanga</i>	<i>Bala Taila</i>	4 days
		<i>Sarvanga Nadi Sweda</i>	<i>Dashmoola Kwatha</i>	4 days
		<i>Virechana Karma</i>	<i>Trivruta Leha with Draksha Jala</i>	1 Days
		<i>Paschat Karma</i>	<i>Sansarjana Krama</i>	3 Days
2.	<i>Shamana Karma</i>	Internal Medication	<i>Manjishthadi Kwath, Gandhaka rasayana + Khadira Churna + Lodhra Churna + Nimba Churna + Guduchi Churna, Avipattikar Churna, Kaishora Guggula</i>	30 Days
		External Medication	<i>Prakshalana with Panchavalkala Kwatha Gandhaka Malahara</i>	30 Days

Shodhana Karma

The *Shodhana Karma* is divided in three steps

a) *Purvakarma*

The *Purvakarma* for *Virechana* include *Deepana Pachana* and *Abhyantara Snehapana*, *Sarvanga Abhyanga* and *Swedana*. The *Deepan Pachana* was done by *Chitrakadi Vati* 1 tablet twice a day with lukewarm water after food for three days. The *Abhyantara Snehapana*

was done with *Go Ghrita* in increasing order. During *Snehapana* patient was advised to take lukewarm water to drink and food advised on *Kshudha Parchiti*. *Lakshna* for *Samyak Snehana* were observed on day 7th of *Abhyantara Snehapana* like *Snigdha Vit*, *Twak Snigdhatata*. Then *Sarvanga Abhyanga* with *Bala Tail* and *Nadi Sweda* was advised for 3 days. The light moong dal khichadi was advised on night before *Virechana*.

b) *Pradhankarma*

Sarvanga Abhyanga and *Nadi Swedana* were done in morning the weight and vitals like heart rate, respiratory rate and blood pressure were noted before administration of *Virechana Aushadha*. The *Virechana Aushadi Trivruta Avleha* 50gm along with *Draksha Jal* was given at 10:00 am. Patient was advised to drink only lukewarm *Draksha Jal* and *Ushna Jal* throughout the day. Total 8 Vegas were observed in patient with *Kaphanta* suggesting *Avara Shudhhi* without any significant complain or any sign of dehydration.

c) ***Pashchat Karma***: As 8 Vegas were observed following *Virechana Karma*, indicating *Avara Shudhhi* a *Sansarjana Karma* was advised for a duration of three days.

Table 2.0: Timeline of the *Shodhana Karma*.

Intervention	Medication	Dose	Duration	Anupana
<i>Deepana-Pachana</i> (27/01/2025- 29/01/2025)	<i>Chitrakadi Vati</i>	1 Tab Twice a day, After food	For 3 days	Lukewarm water
<i>Snehapana</i> (30/02/2025- 05/02/2025)	<i>Go Ghrita</i>	15ml	On 1 st day	
		30ml	On 2 nd day	
		60ml	On 3 rd day	
		90ml	On 4 th day	
		120ml	On 5 th day	
		150ml	On 6 th day	
180ml	On 7 th day			
<i>Sarvanga Abhyanga</i> (06/02/2025- 09/02/2025)	<i>Bala Taila</i>	Q.S. Approx. 20 ml	For 3 days	-
<i>Sarvanga Swedana</i> (06/02/2025- 09/02/2025)	<i>Nadi Sweda</i>	For 5 min	For 3 days	-
<i>Virechana</i> (09/02/2025)	<i>Trivruta Avleha</i>	50 gm	For 1 day	<i>Draksha Jala</i>
<i>Samsarjana Krama</i> (09/02/2025- 11/02/2025)	<i>Peya</i>	According to appetite	<i>Pratham Annakala</i> (Night of <i>Shodhana</i> day)	-
	<i>Vilepi</i>	According to appetite	<i>Dwitivity Annakala</i> <i>Sansarjan</i>	-

			(Morning)	
	<i>Mudga Yusha</i>	According to appetite	<i>Tritiya Annakala</i> (night)	-
	<i>Moong Krushara</i>	According to appetite	<i>Chaturtha Annakala</i> (morning)	-
	<i>Samanya Bhojana</i>	According to appetite	<i>Pancham Annakala</i>	-

Shamana Aushadhi

Abhyantara Shamana Aushadi

The *Abhyantara Shamana Aushadhi* were advised after completion of *Sansarjana Krama* from 12 February to 13 March for 30 Days.

Table No. 3.0: Internal Medication.

Sr. no.	Medicine	Dose	Frequency	Anupana
1.	<i>Manjishthadi Kwath</i>	10ml	Twice a day, empty stomach before food	-
2	<i>Gandhaka rasayana + Khadira Churna + Lodhra Churna + Nimba Churna + Guduchi Churna</i>	65mg+ 1gm+ 500mg+ 500mg+ 250 mg (respectively)	Twice a day, after food	Lukewarm water
3.	<i>Avipattikar Churna</i>	1.5gm	Once a day at night	Lukewarm water
4.	<i>Kaishora Guggula</i>	250mg	Twice a day, before food	<i>Manjishthadi Kwatha</i>

Bahya Parimarjan Chikitsa

Bahya Parimarjana Aushadhi were administered along with *Deepana Pachana* and *Abhyantara Snehapana* for 13 Days. The medications were on hold during *Virechana* and the *Sansarjana Krama* period. Following completion of *Sansarjana Karma*, treatment was resumed with *Abhyantara Shamana Aushadhi* for 30 days.

Table No. 4.0: External medication.

Sr. no.	Medicine	Dose	Frequency	Way of administration
1.	<i>Panchavalkala Kwatha</i>	Q.S.	Twice a day	<i>For Prakshalnartha</i>
2.	<i>Gandhaka Malahara</i>	Q. S.	Twice a day	<i>For Lepa</i>

RESULT

Improvements were observed in *Lakshana* of *Vicharchika* and POEM (Patient-Oriented Eczema Measure) Score and DLQI (Dermatology Life Quality Index) after *Shodhana* and

Shamana Chikitsa. During *Snehapana* itching, roughness of lesion was reduced. The following subjective criteria were studied and evaluated before and after the treatment.

Table 5.0: BT and AT assessment.

S. No.	Subjective Criteria	Before Treatment	After Treatment
1	Skin Discoloration	+++	-
2.	Pain	-	-
3.	Itching	++++	+
4.	Burning Sensation	+++	-
5.	Discharge	++	-
6.	Skin Roughness	++++	+
7.	Skin Thickening	+	-
POEM Score:		17	03
DLQI Score:		24	05

Before Treatment

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

After Treatment

Figure 3

Figure 4

DISCUSSION

As mentioned in Charaka Samhita, *Vicharchika Kushtha* have predominance of *Kapha Dosha* and as per Sushruta Samhita it has predominance of *Pitta Dosha*. The *Lakshana* like *Shyava*, *Pidika*, *Rukshata*, *Kandu* and *Bahustrava* shows strong resemblance with Atopic Eczema having dry and scaly lesion, maculo-papular lesion, severe itching and discharge. The *Kushta* mainly have *Dushti* of *Twak*, *Rakta*, *Mansa* and *Ambu* along with *Tridosha* is mentioned. The *Virechana Karma* has been selected in patient considering *Kapha* and *Pitta* dominance and *Rakta Dushti*.

Probable mode of action of intervention

- 1) *Deepana Pachana*: *Deepana Pachana* was performed using *Chitrakadi Vati*, which possesses *Agni Deepana Pachana* properties along with *Abhyantara Rukshana*, helping to reduce *Kleda* present in *Kushtha*.^[11] It facilitates proper digestion and metabolism, thereby enhancing the absorption and effectiveness of *Abhyantara Snehapana* administered prior to *Shodhana*.
- 2) *Abhyantara Snehapana*: *Abhyantara Snehapana* was carried out using *Go Ghrita*, which helps mobilize the vitiated *Doshas* from the *Shakha* to the *Koshtha*, facilitating their elimination through *Shodhana*. As mentioned in the Charaka Samhita, *Snehapana* is indicated in *Kushtha*. Since *Vicharchika Kushtha* has a predominance of *Pitta and Kapha*, the use of *Go Ghrita* is appropriate due to its *Pittahara* and *Snigdha* properties which also relieves Dryness and scaling of skin.^[12]
- 3) *Abhyanga* and *Swedana*: *Abhyanga* was performed using *Bala Taila*, followed by *Mrudu Nadi Sweda* as *Purvakarma* for *Virechana Karma*. This facilitates the movement of *Doshas* from the *Shakha* to the *Koshta*.
- 4) *Virechana Karma*: *Virechana Karma* is favourable to cure both *Pitta* and *Kapha Dosha*. *Trivrut lehya* is mentioned in Ashtanga Hridayam Kalpa Sthana selected because the *Trivrut* is main ingredient in it and it is *Sukha Virechaka Dravya*. The ingredients of *Trivrut Lehya* are purgatives which increases the water content of faeces by osmotic action and decreases net absorption of water and electrolytes in intestinal mucosa eliminates the toxins from the body. By this regulates the *Vata*, *Pitta*, *Kapha* by causing movement regulation of intestine, chemoenzymatic secretion, intestinal mucosal secretion respectively. Itching, Secretion and Hyperpigmentation are due to *Kapha*, *Pitta* and *Vata Dosha* vitiation these symptoms relived by elimination of the *Dosha* through *Virechana Karma*.^[13]

- 5) *Abhyantara Shamana Chikitsa*: *Manjishthadi Kwatha* is particularly beneficial in conditions where *Rakta Dushti* and *Pitta-Kapha* vitiation are dominant. It is used as an excellent measure for various types of acne problems, eczema and other skin disorders. It helps in preventing eruptions and promoting skin healing. Its anti-inflammatory and detoxifying properties aid in reducing scales, plaques, and itching.^[14] *Gandhak Rasayan* plays a major role in various skin disorders like psoriasis, scabies, eczema, acne, tinea infection and other conditions in *Pittaj Tvakavikara*. it acts as anti-bacterial, anti-viral, anti-pruritic and anti-inflammatory drug.^[15] *Khadira Churna*, *Lodhra Churna*, and *Nimba Churna* act as potent *Rakta Shodhaka* agents, helping to reduce itching and antibacterial effects. *Guduchi Churna* has *Kushthahara* and *Kandughna* actions which treat leprosy and itching.^[16] *Avipattikara Churna*, having *Pitta Kaphahara* and *Mridu Virechaka* properties, aids in the removal of residual *Doshas* and promotes *Srotoshodhana*, thereby controlling furthers *Dosha* aggravation.^[17] *Kaishora Guggulu* through its *Amapachana* action reduces *Ama*, promotes *Raktaprasadana*, and exhibits anti-inflammatory properties, helping to prevent recurrence of symptoms.^[19]
- 6) *Bahya Parimarjan Chikitsa*: *Panchavalkala Kwatha* is used for *Prakshalana* for its Anti-inflammatory, Analgesic and Antimicrobial properties. The constituents in the *Panchavalkala* might have helped in regression of signs and symptom of Eczema.^[19] *Gandhak Malahara* possesses *Tridosahara*, *Snigdha*, *Teekshna*, *Ruksha*, *Sara* and *Ushna* properties. All the ingredients have pharmacologically antifungal, antimicrobial and antioxidant action, thus it can effectively reduce infections and prevent its recurrence by improving the immunity of skin with its antioxidant property. *Shuddha Gandhaka* is antifungal and antimicrobial, it helps in detoxification and tissue repair.^[20]

CONCLUSION

The quality of life of the patient and present symptoms showed marked improvement in symptoms and POEM and DLQI score with therapeutic purgation by *Trivruta Avleha* followed by *Shamana Aushadha* without any adverse reaction to the treatment. The case report concludes that Ayurveda management of *Vicharchika* Atopic Dermatitis is effective and can be explored further through an extensive, robust clinical protocol.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I sincerely acknowledge HOD, Professor, Dept. of Kaumarbhritya, ITRA, Jamnagar.

FINANCIAL SUPPORT AND SPONSORSHIP

Nil.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest.

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